

Guidelines for maintaining blood glucose control in adult patients with COVID-19 given dexamethasone

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Introduction

There is a higher risk of dysglycaemia for patients with COVID-19 and pre-existing diabetes. There is also a higher risk of stress hyperglycaemia in patients with COVID-19 without a history of pre-existing diabetes.

Dexamethasone and other steroids (e.g. hydrocortisone, methylprednisolone, prednisolone) are being used to manage patients with COVID-19 who require oxygen. Maintaining good blood glucose control during this time is essential to improve clinical outcomes.

This guideline describes the management strategy of glucose control in adult patients with COVID-19 given dexamethasone (or hydrocortisone).

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Guidelines for maintaining blood glucose control in patients with COVID-19 given dexamethasone

1 Target population:

- Any adult patient (≥ 18 years old) receiving or about to receive dexamethasone as part of management of as set out in COVID-19 Guide for Medicine.
- This protocol is not applicable in pregnant women with COVID-19. For dysglycaemia in pregnancy discuss with the diabetes team.
- NICE (NG159) recommended steroids treatment course for management of people with severe or critical COVID-19.
 - dexamethasone 6mg PO/IV OD for 7-10 days
 - hydrocortisone 50mg IV TDS for 7-10 days
- Use this protocol to optimise glucose control while patients are on dexamethasone. Use the same principles if hydrocortisone is used.
- Other steroids may be used (e.g. methylprednisolone, prednisolone etc.). Consult the diabetes team as the plan depends on the dose and frequency of the steroids.

2 First steps: ensure the following steps are done

- Check blood glucose: capillary blood glucose (CBG) or from blood gases analysis.
- If blood glucose >11 mmol/L then:
 - Check ketones (exclude diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) and calculate osmolality (exclude hyperosmolar hyperglycaemic state (HHS)). Some patient may have mixed DKA/HHS:
 - HHS: calculate plasma osmolality ($2Na + Urea + Glucose$); if ≥ 320 mOsm/kg then treat for HHS and then check for ketones to exclude mixed HHS/DKA.
 - DKA: Check blood ketones if blood glucose >11 mmol/L:
 - Blood ketone >1.5 mmol/L \rightarrow Inform doctor for clinical assessment (risk of impending DKA).
 - Blood ketone ≥ 3.0 mmol/L \rightarrow inform doctor and treat for DKA.
 - For how to treat DKA and/or HHS refer to the diabetes emergencies protocol ('pink sheet')
 - Send HbA1c (separate EDTA bottle) to the lab.
- **Pregnancy and COVID-19:**
 - The blood glucose monitoring and targets in pregnancy are different due to the high risk of worse fetal, perinatal and maternal outcomes with hyperglycaemia.
 - Therefore, for all pregnant women with COVID-19 please follow the following plan:
 - Check CBG 4 times per day: pre breakfast and 1 hour after meals.
 - Ensure hands are clean
 - Refer to the Diabetes Pregnancy Team (bleep 362 or Diabetes Consultant on call) for any of the following:
 - A single reading ≥ 10 mmol/L and/or if there are 2 readings above 7.8 mmol/L
 - HbA1c of ≥ 42 mmol/mol ($\geq 6\%$).

3 Therapy aim target range for blood glucose

- Maintain blood glucose 6 – 11 mmol/L
- Check blood glucose at pre-breakfast (0600-0900), pre-lunch (1200-1300), pre-evening meal (1700-1900), and at 2200 hours. Prescribe on EPMA using the 'dexamethasone COVID' orderset. Check at 0300 hours if on insulin or there was hypoglycaemia (<4 mmol/l) in the last 24 hours.
- Treat as for hypoglycaemia if blood glucose is <4 mmol/L as per the Trust protocol.
- Individualise treatments based on clinical condition and frailty.

4 The guidelines navigator

Management pathway of blood glucose control in adult patients (≥18 years old) with COVID-19 & prescribed dexamethasone
(For pregnant women: see section 2 for details on monitoring and referral pathway)

Dexamethasone is indicated? Prescribe dexamethasone using the 'dexamethasone COVID' orderset on EPR (dexamethasone 6mg po/iv once a day (morning) for 7-10 days, blood glucose monitoring, PRN Novorapid®, hypoglycaemia bundle). Check HbA1c

Use this protocol when hydrocortisone 50mg IV TDS course is prescribed. Other steroids may be used e.g. methylprednisolone and prednisolone. Use the same principles and consult the diabetes team for specific advice.

Add Humulin-I® to regular diabetes treatments as follows.

Patient already on insulin or T1DM (more details in section 6.2): KEEP USUAL INSULIN BUT ADD HUMULIN-I as follows:

- To avoid in-hospital DKA/HHS keep usual basal insulin going but ADD Humulin-I®. Examples of usual basal/background insulins: Detemir (Levemir®), Glargine (Lantus®/Abasaglar®), Degludec (Tresiba®), Glargine 300units/ml (Toujeo®), Insulatard®, Humulin-I®, Insuman Basal®
- Stop bolus insulin (Novorapid®, Humalog®, Apidra®, Humulin-S®, Actrapid®) if patient NOT eating.

Patients on oral diabetes treatments (see section 6.1; table 2): Stop metformin (AKI, eGFR <30, lactate >4mmol/L), **stop SGLT2 inhibitors** (any acutely unwell patient), **stop sulfonylureas** (e.g. gliclazide) if patient not eating or on high flow O2 (≥40%)/CPAP.

Maintain blood glucose 6-11 mmol/L Treat as for hypoglycaemia if CBG <4 mmol/L (see Trust protocol)

Dexamethasone course is to be stopped/alterd or patient to be discharged? (section 9)

- Reduce the prescription of PRN Novorapid® by 50% if not on steroids and patient is staying in hospital.
- Review need to restart stopped diabetes medications/insulin before discharge.
- Stop Humulin-I® when dexamethasone is stopped. **Caution:** Those who presented with DKA/HHS or HbA1c ≥86mmol/mol (≥10%) will need insulin (discuss with diabetes before stopping insulin).
- Reduce the prescription of PRN Novorapid® by 50% (if not on steroids and staying in hospital).
- Review need to restart stopped diabetes medications/insulin before discharge.

- Refer to the inpatient diabetes team:**
- Patients admitted with DKA and/or HHS.
 - Patients on dexamethasone & on Humulin-I® (this protocol).
 - Patients who require education on use of insulin and/or CBG monitoring.
 - If switching to a different steroids course or higher/lower doses.
 - CBGs >20 or <4 mmol/L despite adjustments to treatment.
 - New or alterations to enteral/parenteral feeding.
 - Patients on insulin pump.
 - Pregnant women with a single reading ≥10 OR >7.8mmol/L (x2) OR HbA1c ≥42mmol/mol (≥6%).

- EPR referrals to inpatient diabetes teams**
 "Diabetes inpatient referral" @Denmark hill OR @PRUH
- Bleeps:**
- Denmark hill:
 - Diabetes nurses (301) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700],
 - Inpatient diabetes SPR (122) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700; Sat-Sun 1000-1800].
 - PRUH: DSN (764) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700]

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5 How to order dexamethasone COVID bundle on EPR

- Patients on dexamethasone should have their blood glucose monitored.
- Type 'dexamethasone COVID' in Sunrise EPR 'orders' section.
- The prescription bundle includes:
 - A prescription for dexamethasone 6mg orally/intravenous for 7-10 days.
 - Regular blood glucose monitoring (@0600, 1200, 1800, 2200 hours). Advice to check at 0300 hours if patient on insulin or experienced hypoglycaemia the day before.
 - A prescription for supplemental fast acting insulin (Novorapid®) to treat hyperglycaemia.
 - Hypoglycaemia treatments bundle (oral hypoglycaemia treatment, Glucose 10%, Glucose 20%, Glucagon).

6 Need to start regular Humulin-I® subcutaneous insulin when blood glucose >11mmol/L

Choose the patient group: A or B:

6.1 Group A (insulin naïve): Patients not known to have diabetes or have T2DM on oral treatments:

- Patients with type 2 diabetes on oral medications should have the following actions undertaken as per **Table 1**.
Start Humulin-I® twice daily based on patient weight as per **Table 2**.

Table 1: type 2 diabetes medications adjustments.

Medication group	When to stop	When to restart
Metformin	Acute kidney injury OR eGFR ≤30 OR lactate >4 mmol/L	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • eGFR improved to >30 OR AKI resolved. • Then assess Lactate as part of holistic clinical assessment. If improving and lactate <4 mmol/L and renal parameters above are fulfilled then can restart Metformin.
SGLT2 inhibitors (e.g. dapagliflozin, empagliflozin, canagliflozin, sotagliflozin, ertugliflozin)	Always stop in acutely unwell patients.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restart on discharge if clinically well. • NOT to restart if patient presented in DKA. To add to discharge summary for GP/diabetes clinic review (if under diabetes service).
Sulfonylureas (e.g. gliclazide, glipizide, glibenclamide, glimepiride, tolbutamide)	Patient not eating Patient on high flow oxygen (>40%) OR CPAP	Clinically improving and able to eat meals.
DPP4 inhibitors (e.g. sitagliptin, saxagliptin, linagliptin)	Continue unless there is acute kidney injury (sitagliptin, saxagliptin) OR acute liver failure (linagliptin)	On resolution of acute kidney injury or acute liver failure.

Table 2: Humulin-I® doses for patients not known to have diabetes or have T2DM on oral treatments (Group A: insulin naïve)

Actual or estimated body weight (kg)	Age ≤70 years AND eGFR >30		Age >70 OR eGFR ≤30	
	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)
<45kg	Discuss insulin dosing with the diabetes team. Risk of hypoglycaemia.			
45-60 kg	9 units	5 units	4 units	2 units
61-70 kg	12 units	6 units	6 units	3 units
71-80 kg	19 units	10 units	9 units	5 units
81-100 kg	27 units	14 units	13 units	7 units
101-120 kg	33 units	17 units	17 units	9 units
>120 kg	40 units	21 units	20 units	10 units

6.2 Group B: Patients who are already on insulin or T1DM

- In this group the aim is to add Humulin-I® to cover the effect of dexamethasone for COVID-19 rather than adjust the patient's own insulin. The Humulin-I® course is an addition to the usual insulin regimen while patients on dexamethasone. When dexamethasone is stopped, it is safer to stop Humulin-I® and not risk DKA/HHS or adverse incidents by stopping the patient's own insulin.
- For oral medications adjustments see Table 1
- Patient's pre-existing regimens:
 - Basal bolus insulin regimen:
 - To avoid in hospital DKA/HHS, keep usual basal/background insulin going and ADD Humulin-I® (to cover dexamethasone for COVID-19): Examples of basal insulins Detemir (Levemir®), Glargine (Lantus®/Abasaglar®), Degludec (Tresiba®), Glargine 300units/ml (Toujeo®), Insulatard®, Humulin-I®, or Insuman Basal®, to avoid in-hospital DKA/HHS.
 - Stop bolus insulin (Novorapid®, Humalog®, Apidra®, Humulin-S®, Actrapid®) if patient NOT eating.
 - Basal/background insulin only or basal+oral medications: keep the basal insulin going and adjust oral medications as in section 6.1.
 - Pre-mixed insulin (e.g. Novomix30®, HumalogMix50®, HumalogMix25®, HumulinM3®): discuss with the diabetes team for individualised approach particularly if patient not eating.
- If patient is not eating, or on FiO2 ≥40% or CPAP then:
 - Withhold mealtime insulin (Novorapid®, Humalog®, Apidra®).
 - Convert pre-mixed insulin (e.g. Novomix30®, HumalogMix25®, HumalogMix50®) to Insulatard/Humulin-I® and refer to the inpatient diabetes team.
- You will need the total amount of all insulins the patient normally uses in a day to choose the correct amount from the **table 3** below. If patient is too ill or vomiting or unable to accurately estimate total insulin requirements then to consider alternatives e.g. VRIII ('insulin sliding scale').

Table 3: Added Humulin-I® doses for patients who are already on insulin or T1DM (Group B).

Step 1: Calculate insulin total daily dose (TDD) currently taken by the patient (usual insulin regimen) [units]	Step 2: Identify the characteristics of the patient and ADD Humulin-I® to their usual insulin			
	Age ≤70 years AND eGFR >30		Age >70 OR eGFR ≤30	
	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)
<30 units	5 units	3 units	3 units	0
30-50 units	6 units	3 units	3 units	2 units
50-75 units	10 units	5 units	5 units	3 units
76-100 units	15 units	8 units	8 units	4 units
>100 units	22 units	11 units	11 units	6 units

7 Supplemental fast acting insulin (Novorapid®) doses to correct hyperglycaemia (>11 mmol/L)

- From the COVID dexamethasone orderset, a prescription for supplemental fast acting insulin (Novorapid®) will be generated.

- Complete the relevant fields for the required Novorapid® dose to correct hyperglycaemia (>11, >15 and >20 mmol/L).
- Use the table below to populate the fields. The values in the boxes will be pre-populated with the doses from TDD<50units (can be edited).

- Threshold 1: >11mmol/L:

Type of Insulin
 Novorapid (insulin Aspart) ↓

If blood glucose >
 11 mmol/L after meals, bedtime or 3am

Dose:
 [] unit(s)

- Threshold 2: >15 mmol/L

Type of Insulin
 Novorapid (insulin Aspart) ↓

If blood glucose >
 15 mmol/L after meals, bedtime or 3am

Dose:
 [] unit(s)

- Threshold 3: >20 mmol/L

If blood glucose >
 20 mmol/L after meals, bedtime or 3am

Dose:
 [] unit(s)

The spaces highlighted by “” will be pre-populated with the lowest values from the “TDD <50 units/day OR weight <50kg” category (Can be amended). For other bands use the **Table 4** after considering the following:

- If patient is insulin naïve, use the weight to calculate the dose. Otherwise, use total daily insulin dose for dose calculation (add up all the insulin doses that the patient takes in a day).
- Repeat CBG measurement after 2 hours. Give another supplemental dose as per table above if CBG still >11 mmol/l.
- Check capillary **KETONES** when CBG ≥11 mmol/L. Send bloods (VBGs, renal profile) to rule out HHS if CBG >20 mmol/L

Table 4: Supplemental fast acting insulin dose (Novorapid®) based on patient’s total daily insulin dose (TDD) (or weight if TDD is not known).

Capillary blood glucose threshold (mmol/L)	Total daily insulin dose (TDD) <50units/day OR Weight <50 kg	Total daily insulin dose (TDD) 50-100units OR Weight 50-100 kg	Total daily insulin dose (TDD) >100 units OR Weight >100 kg
	Novorapid® dose	Novorapid® dose	Novorapid® dose
11.1-14.9	2 units	4 units	5 units
15-19.9	4 units	6 units	7 units
20 or above	6 units	8 units	10 units

When the dexamethasone course is finished, the Novorapid® supplemental insulin doses should be halved.

8 How to adjust insulin Humulin-I® if CBGs continue to be out of the treatment range 6-11 mmol/L.

- Review Humulin-I® doses every 24hours.
- Review need to adjust the supplemental Novorapid® every 24 hours.
- Adjust the insulin Humulin-I® dose according to the chart below (Figure 1).

Figure 1: How to adjust insulin Humulin-I® if CBGs continue to be out of the treatment range 6-11 mmol/L.

9 When dexamethasone course is coming to an end or discharge is planned

General principles

- It is important to individualise care for patients with COVID-19 and hyperglycaemia/diabetes as their condition changes.
- Insulin resistance will begin to fall as the patients with COVID-19 start to improve.
- **Humulin-I® can be stopped when the dexamethasone course is stopped.** The exception is in people with no previous history of diabetes people who will likely require insulin after discharge (presented with DKA/HHS, high HbA1c ≥ 86 mmol/mol ($\geq 10\%$)). Those should be referred to the diabetes team for review of ongoing therapy.
- Dexamethasone for COVID-19 should not exceed 10 days unless specifically agreed with the respiratory team as per the COVID-19 protocol. For patients receiving steroids for more than 10 days, they might need a weaning steroids regimen due to risk of adrenal suppression.
- If switching to an alternative steroids course consult the diabetes team.
- Some patients with steroid induced hyperglycaemia may go on to develop type 2 diabetes later. Important to alert the GP to check HbA1c 3-6 months after discharge and then annually (write on discharge summary).

Ward teams responsibility

- Inform/refer inpatient diabetes team about all patients on dexamethasone who require Humulin-I.
- Review blood glucose values every 24 hours to adjust insulin doses.
- If switching to a different steroids course or higher/lower doses, consult the diabetes team.
- Aim to restart previous medications if they were stopped or withheld provided there are no contraindications or reasons to stop (e.g. SGLT2 inhibitors in patients presenting with DKA).
- Ensure patient's telephone number(s) and email are documented on EPR/PiMS/clinical notes in order to contact the patient after discharge.

Diabetes team responsibilities

- Review patients for need of ongoing insulin therapy, further dose adjustments if BGs are not in range despite adjustments made or need for further therapies on discharge.
- Provide relevant insulin and blood glucose monitoring training.
- Review need for diabetes follow-up.
- A small group of patients may need a short course of gliclazide on discharge if unable to administer insulin or requiring small doses of insulin. Caution in elderly >70 years and/or chronic kidney disease, low eGFR <30 . Dose and duration will be specified by the diabetes team and documented in the clinical notes.

For discharge summary

- On the discharge summary please write: GP to check HbA1c 3 months after discharge and then every year.
- Ensure patient's previous medications have been reviewed and reinstated properly. If patient was on SGLT2 inhibitors and presented in DKA, these should not be restarted on discharge (risk of recurrent DKA).
- NOT for TTA unless specifically instructed by the diabetes team:
 - Supplemental Novorapid®.
 - Hypoglycaemia bundle: oral hypoglycaemia treatment, Glucose 10%, Glucose 20%, Glucagon.

10 When to refer to the inpatient diabetes team:

- Patients admitted with DKA and/or HHS.
- Patients on dexamethasone & on Humulin-I® (this protocol).
- Patients who require education on use of insulin and/or blood glucose monitoring.
- If switching to a different steroids course.
- Blood glucose continues to be >20 or <4 mmol/L despite adjustments to treatment.
- New or alterations to enteral/parenteral feeding.
- Patients on continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion (CSII) pump therapy ('insulin pump').
- Pregnant women with a single reading ≥ 10 OR >7.8 mmol/L (x2) OR HbA1c ≥ 42 mmol/mol ($\geq 6\%$).

11 How to contact inpatient diabetes teams

- EPR referrals: Diabetes inpatient referral @Denmark hill **OR** @PRUH
- Bleeps:
 - Denmark hill:
 - Diabetes nurses (301) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700],
 - Inpatient diabetes SPR (122) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700; Sat-Sun 1000-1800].
 - PRUH: DSN (764) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700]
 - Cross-site out of these hours call the diabetes consultant oncall via switchboard.

12 References

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13 Appendix 1: guidelines pathway and summary guide

Two sides of A4 sized paper to be used by in conjunction with this document as a quick guide.

Management pathway of blood glucose control in adult patients (≥18 years old) with COVID-19 & prescribed dexamethasone

(For pregnant women: see [section 2](#) for details on monitoring and referral pathway)

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Dexamethasone is indicated? Prescribe dexamethasone using the 'dexamethasone COVID' orderset on EPR (dexamethasone 6mg po/iv once a day (morning) for 7-10 days, blood glucose monitoring, PRN Novorapid®, hypoglycaemia bundle). Check HbA1c

Use this protocol when hydrocortisone 50mg IV TDS course is prescribed. Other steroids may be used e.g. methylprednisolone and prednisolone. Use the same principles and consult the diabetes team for specific advice.

Add Humulin-I® to regular diabetes treatments as follows.

Patient already on insulin or T1DM (more details in [section 6.2](#)): KEEP USUAL INSULIN BUT ADD HUMULIN-I as follows:

- To avoid in-hospital DKA/HHS keep usual basal insulin going but ADD Humulin-I®. Examples of usual basal/background insulins: Detemir (Levemir®), Glargine (Lantus®/Abasaglar®), Degludec (Tresiba®), Glargine 300units/ml (Toujeo®), Insulatard®, Humulin-I®, or Insuman Basal®
- Stop bolus insulin (Novorapid®, Humalog®, Apidra®, Humulin-S®, Actrapid®) if patient NOT eating.

Patients on oral diabetes treatments (see [section 6.1](#); [table 2](#)): Stop metformin (AKI, eGFR <30, lactate >4mmol/L), **stop SGLT2 inhibitors** (any acutely unwell patient), **stop sulfonylureas** (e.g. gliclazide) if patient not eating or on high flow O2 (≥40%)/CPAP.

Maintain blood glucose 6-11 mmol/L

Treat as for hypoglycaemia if CBG <4 mmol/L (see Trust protocol)

Refer to the inpatient diabetes team:

- Patients admitted with DKA and/or HHS.
- Patients on dexamethasone & on Humulin-I® (this protocol).
- Patients who require education on use of insulin and/or CBG monitoring.
- If switching to a different steroids course or higher/lower doses.
- CBGs >20 or <4 mmol/L despite adjustments to treatment.
- New or alterations to enteral/parenteral feeding.
- Patients on insulin pump.
- Pregnant women with a single reading ≥10 OR >7.8mmol/L (x2) OR HbA1c ≥42mmol/mol (≥6%).

EPR referrals to inpatient diabetes teams

"Diabetes inpatient referral" @Denmark hill OR @PRUH

Bleeps:

- Denmark hill:
 - Diabetes nurses (301) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700],
 - Inpatient diabetes SPR (122) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700; Sat-Sun 1000-1800].
- PRUH: DSN (764) [Mon-Fri 0900-1700]

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Management pathway of blood glucose control in adult patients (≥18 years old) with COVID-19 & prescribed dexamethasone

For patients who need Dexamethasone as part of COVID-19 treatment

Type 'dexamethasone COVID' in EPR orders; The bundle contains Dexamethasone course (6mg po/iv od), glucose monitoring, supplemental Novorapid®, hypoglycaemia bundle. Check HbA1c

Maintain blood glucose 6-11 mmol/L; treat as for hypoglycaemia when CBG <4mmol/L

Table 1: Type 2 diabetes medications adjustments

Medication group	When to stop	When to restart
Metformin	Acute kidney injury OR eGFR ≤30 OR lactate >4 mmol/L	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> eGFR improved to >30 OR AKI resolved. Then assess Lactate as part of holistic clinical assessment. If improving and lactate <4 mmol/L and renal parameters above are fulfilled then can restart Metformin.
SGLT2 inhibitors (e.g. dapagliflozin, empagliflozin, canagliflozin, sotagliflozin, ertugliflozin)	Always stop in acutely unwell patients.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restart on discharge if clinically well. NOT to restart if patient presented in DKA. To add to discharge summary for GP/diabetes clinic review (if under diabetes service).
Sulfonylureas (e.g. gliclazide, glipizide, glibenclamide, glimepiride, tolbutamide)	Patient not eating Patient on high flow oxygen (>40%) OR CPAP	Clinically improving and able to eat meals.
DPP4 inhibitors (e.g. sitagliptin, saxagliptin, linagliptin)	Continue unless there is acute kidney injury (sitagliptin, saxagliptin) OR acute liver failure (linagliptin)	On resolution of acute kidney injury or acute liver failure.

Table 2: Humulin-I® doses for patients not known to have diabetes or have T2DM on oral treatments (Group A: insulin naïve)

Actual or estimated body weight (kg)	Age ≤70 years AND eGFR >30		Age >70 OR eGFR ≤30	
	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)
<45kg	Discuss insulin dosing with the diabetes team. Risk of hypoglycaemia.			
45-60 kg	9 units	5 units	4 units	2 units
61-70 kg	12 units	6 units	6 units	3 units
71-80 kg	19 units	10 units	9 units	5 units
81-100 kg	27 units	14 units	13 units	7 units
101-120 kg	33 units	17 units	17 units	9 units
>120 kg	40 units	21 units	20 units	10 units

Table 3: Added Humulin-I® doses for patients who are already on insulin or T1DM (Group B).

Step 1: Calculate insulin total daily dose (TDD) currently taken by the patient (usual insulin regimen) [units]	Step 2: Identify the characteristics of the patient and ADD Humulin-I® to their usual insulin			
	Age ≤70 years AND eGFR >30		Age >70 OR eGFR ≤30	
	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe pre-breakfast Humulin-I® dose (units)	Prescribe bedtime Humulin-I® dose (units)
<30 units	5 units	3 units	3 units	0
30-50 units	6 units	3 units	3 units	2 units
50-75 units	10 units	5 units	5 units	3 units
76-100 units	15 units	8 units	8 units	4 units
>100 units	22 units	11 units	11 units	6 units

Table 4: Supplemental fast acting insulin (Novorapid®) dose based on patient's insulin total daily dose (TDD) (or weight if TDD is not known).

Capillary blood glucose threshold (mmol/L)	Total daily insulin dose (TDD)	Total daily insulin dose (TDD)	Total daily insulin dose (TDD)
	<50units/day (OR Weight <50 kg)	50-100units (OR Weight 50-100 kg)	>100 units (OR Weight >100 kg)
	Novorapid® dose	Novorapid® dose	Novorapid® dose
11.1-14.9	2 units	4 units	5 units
15-19.9	4 units	6 units	7 units
20 or above	6 units	8 units	10 units

Figure 1: How to adjust insulin Humulin-I® if CBGs continue to be out of the treatment range 6-11 mmol/L.

To be used in conjunction with the King's gguidelines for maintaining blood glucose control in patients with COVID-19 given dexamethasone